

NEW APPROACHES TO ASSESSING ORAL COMMUNICATION IN PROJECT ASSIGNMENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AT THE UNIVERSITY*Lysytska O.,**PhD, Associate Professor**Associate Professor of Foreign Language Department**Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University**Ukraine, Kharkiv****Romantsova Ya.****PhD, Associate Professor**Associate Professor of Foreign Language Department**Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University**Ukraine, Kharkiv***Abstract**

The article substantiates a process-oriented model for assessing oral foreign language communication of first-year university students during poster presentation projects in the context of active AI use. Based on diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment stages, the model shifts focus from the final product to the dynamics of communicative competence development. Quantitative results demonstrate positive growth across all criteria, particularly interactivity and communicative strategies, confirming the effectiveness and validity of process-based assessment in project-oriented language learning.

Keywords: oral communication, foreign language assessment, process-oriented assessment, formative assessment, project-based learning, poster presentation, communicative competence, artificial intelligence in education.

Introduction

In the context of the transformation of higher education and the active introduction of digital technologies, the problem of assessing oral foreign language communication is becoming particularly relevant. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages are focused on competency-based, communicative, and project-oriented approaches, within which oral speech is considered not as a reproduction of language forms, but as a means of solving academic and professional tasks (Council of Europe, 2020).

Project assignments, in particular poster presentations, are widely used in university teaching of a foreign language at the initial stages of study, including the first year. They allow combining the development of language skills with the formation of the skills of cooperation, critical thinking, and public speaking (Council of Europe, 2020). At the same time, practice shows that the assessment of such tasks, as before, is often focused on the final result - the final oral performance or visual product.

The situation is complicated by the widespread use of artificial intelligence tools by students, which questions the validity of assessment focused exclusively on the product of activity. In this regard, there is a need to rethink approaches to assessing oral project tasks and move the emphasis from the final result to the process of educational communication, which includes discussion, planning, oral interaction and phased preparation of the speech and presentation.

In this situation the assessment of the aspects of educational activity that cannot be fully automated is of the particular importance: oral interaction, communicative strategies, participation in discussions, argumentation, the ability to respond to questions and adapt the text to the audience.

In this respect, the purpose of this study is to describe and substantiate a process-oriented model of assessing oral communication within the framework of preparing a poster presentation, in which the object of assessment is not only the final speech, but also the dynamics of the development of communicative competence at different stages of project work, starting from discussing the idea and planning the content to rehearsals and final presentation of the poster.

The article proposes a multi-stage model for assessing oral communication of first-year students, which includes diagnostic, formative, and summative stages and is based on the principles of formative and criterion-based assessment.

Literature review

The issue of assessing oral communicative competence in higher education is at the center of attention of modern foreign language teaching methodology. Scientific research of recent decades emphasizes the need to move from traditional summative control to formative and authentic assessment, focused on the learning process and the development of communicative skills.

Formative assessment in language education.

Formative assessment occupies a central place in modern theory and practice of language education. Unlike summative control, focused on fixing the final result, formative assessment is aimed at supporting the learning process and developing students' communicative skills (Pinto-Llorente & Izquierdo-Álvarez, 2024). Studies emphasize that regular, dialogic feedback contributes to the conscious development of oral speech, increases students' motivation and forms their autonomy (Winstone & Carless, 2019).

In the context of oral communication assessment, formative assessment is implemented through observations, analytical rubrics, self-assessment and peer assessment, which allows recording students' progress

over time, and not just the level of language proficiency at a specific moment (Fulcher, 2015). Thus, oral communication is viewed as a developing skill, and assessment as an integral part of the learning process (Pinto-Llorente & Izquierdo-Álvarez, 2024).

Formative assessment is viewed in the scientific literature as a tool for developing competences, and not just as a means of setting a final score (Wiliam, 2011; Harding & Kremmel, 2016; Winstone & Carless, 2019; Panadero et al., 2018).

Assessment of oral communication and the CEFR. The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) has significantly influenced modern approaches to the assessment of oral communication in higher education. The CEFR offers descriptors of speech that focus on the functional use of language in real-life communicative situations, including interaction, spontaneity and pragmatic adequacy (Council of Europe, 2020).

Current research emphasizes the need to interpret CEFR levels not as static categories, but as guidelines for the process-based assessment of oral language development (Fan & Yan, 2020). In project tasks, CEFR descriptors are used as a basis for developing analytical criteria that allow assessing student participation in discussions, presentations, and collaborative work (Brooks, 2009; Galaczi et al., 2011). This approach increases the transparency of assessment and its relevance to the real communicative tasks of university education.

The conclusions from these sources allow us to state that modern assessment of communication takes into account the student's activity in the dialogue, his participation in interaction and adaptive response, and not only the final product of the utterance (Council of Europe, 2020; Brooks, 2009; Galaczi et al., 2011).

Project-based and task-based learning as an assessment context. Project-based learning and task-based language teaching are considered in modern literature as the optimal context for assessing oral communication. Project tasks create authentic communicative situations in which oral speech is used as a means to achieve a common goal, and not as an object of isolated testing (Beckett & Miller, 2020).

Within the framework of project activities, assessment of oral communication is integrated and includes presentations, group discussions, negotiations and reflection. Researchers note that it is in such conditions that formative assessment is most effective, as it allows taking into account the interactive and social aspects of speech, as well as developing students' strategic and sociolinguistic competence (O'Dowd & O'Rourke, 2019).

Scientific publications on competency-based and project-based approaches emphasize that it is oral communication in the process of activity that is key to the development of communicative competence (Beckett & Miller, 2020; Stoller, 2006).

Assessment in the context of digitalization and the use of AI. The digitalization of higher education and the active implementation of artificial intelligence tools are significantly changing approaches to assessing language skills. However, modern research indicates

the limited capabilities of AI in assessing oral communication, especially in terms of interactivity, pragmatics, and contextual interpretation of utterances (Selwyn, 2023).

Although automated systems are able to analyze individual speech parameters (e.g. pronunciation or pace), they do not fully reflect communicative competence as a socially and situationally conditioned skill (Stoynoff & Chapelle, 2021). A theoretical review of communicative competence in AI conditions emphasizes that modern communication skills go beyond traditional tests, requiring the assessment of real-life interaction and the use of digital tools (Poole & Mackworth, 2023). In this regard, oral communication in project tasks is considered the most valid object of assessment, requiring teacher participation and the use of formative, human-centered approaches. The British Council notes in its analytical material that AI is transforming the assessment of oral speech, including interactive tasks, adaptive feedback and analysis of speech activity (British Council, 2025).

Researchers emphasize that in the AI era, the importance of speaking as an indicator of real language proficiency is not decreasing, but, on the contrary, increasing (Fan & Yan, 2020).

In AI scientific sources, it is noted that oral communication is becoming a key valid area of assessment, as AI environments require flexibility, interaction and adaptation, which are difficult to measure through traditional methods (Selwyn, 2023; Holmes et al., 2019).

In this context, oral communication and process-based assessment are seen as key tools for ensuring academic integrity and the authenticity of learning outcomes (Ajjawi & Boud, 2017; Bearman et al., 2020).

Methods

The study has a quasi-experimental design using quantitative methods of analysis and elements of a pedagogical experiment. The aim of the study is to verify the effectiveness of a process-oriented model of assessing oral communication of first-year university students during the preparation of a poster presentation in a foreign language in conditions of active use of digital tools and elements of artificial intelligence.

The subject of the study is the dynamics of the development of oral communication of students during staged (diagnostic-formative-summative) assessment.

Study participants

The experiment was participated in by 48 first-year students of the law specialty of Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, who study a foreign language at level B2 according to the CEFR. The students were united in 12 small project groups of 3–5 people to perform a joint task of preparing a poster presentation.

Data collection tools

The following tools were used to collect empirical data: 1) an analytical multilevel analytical scale (analytical rubric) for assessing oral communication, developed taking into account the CEFR descriptors (Companion Volume) and adapted to the tasks of project-based learning and the poster presentation format. It included six criteria: communicative clarity; organization of oral expression; lexical and grammatical adequacy; interactivity; use of communicative strategies; academic and ethical correctness (taking into account the

use of AI); 2) an oral communication portfolio, which includes oral tasks, written speech plans and working notes of students; 3) teacher observation, structured according to the developed criteria.

Each criterion was assessed on a scale of 1 to 4. The scores reflected the degree of development of each component of communicative competence and showed a progression from elementary to more autonomous and conscious use of oral speech in an academic context (1 - elementary proficiency; requires significant support; 2 - basic proficiency; understands and expresses simple ideas, errors do not interfere with communication; 3 - confident use; ideas are coherent, partially adapts to the audience; 4 - autonomous, accurate, and coherent use of the skill).

The analytical nature of the rubric provided for separate assessment of individual components of oral communication, which made it possible to track the dynamics of the development of each aspect of communicative competence at the diagnostic, formative, and summative stages of project work.

The rubric was used as a teaching assessment tool, and was also used in self-assessment and peer assessment procedures, which corresponded to the principles of assessment formation and contributed to the development of students' educational autonomy.

The Analytic Scale included the following criteria:

1) *communicative clarity* (clarity and accuracy of expression of thought, logical coherence of the statement, use of adaptive strategies in response to audience questions);

2) *organization of oral expression* (structuring of the speech, presence of a clear introduction, main part and conclusions, logical transitions between semantic blocks, compliance with the rules);

3) *lexical and grammatical adequacy* (diversity and relevance of vocabulary, grammatical correctness, pronunciation and intonation accuracy);

4) *interactivity* (ability to maintain the audience's attention, ask clarifying questions, adequately respond to listeners' requests and effectively manage the time of the speech);

5) *use of communicative strategies* (ability to perform the roles of project leader, discussion moderator and speaker, as well as to effectively cooperate in a team);

6) *academic and ethical correctness* (compliance with the norms of academic communication, correct presentation of sources and results of work, responsible and conscious use of artificial intelligence tools).

Research Procedure

The study was conducted over one training module (4 weeks) and included three consecutive assessment stages: diagnostic, formative, and summative.

At the *diagnostic stage*, students performed a 2–3 minute mini-presentation, which included a summary of the key ideas of the poster and answers to the teacher's questions. This format allowed determining the initial level of oral communicative competence. An example of a mini-presentation prepared by a group of students is presented in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Slide of a mini-presentation at the diagnostic level of the study

The formative stage covered the process of preparing a poster presentation and included group discussions, rehearsals of oral fragments, and reflective written reports. Assessment at this stage was formative in

nature and was aimed at supporting the development of oral communication and students' awareness of the criteria for their successful performance. A detailed plan of the students' presentation is presented in *Figure 2*.

Oral Presentation Plan (5–7 minutes)

“SHOULD ALL LAWS BE THE SAME IN EVERY COUNTRY?”

Section	Time	Key Ideas	Presentation Text
Title	10 sec	Topic introduction	<i>Today I will talk about whether all laws should be the same in every country.</i>
Introduction	50–60 sec	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laws organize social life • Different legal systems 	<i>Laws organize social life and help maintain order. However, legal systems are different in each country. This raises the question of whether laws should be the same everywhere or different.</i>
Arguments FOR the Same Laws	1–1.5 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equal rights for all • International cooperation • Strong human rights protection 	<i>Supporters of the same laws argue that they ensure equal rights for all people. Common laws can improve international cooperation and strengthen human rights protection. This is especially important in a globalized world.</i>
Human Rights	1–1.5 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universal basic rights • Life, freedom, dignity • Global agreements 	<i>Human rights are often considered universal. Basic rights such as life, freedom, and human dignity should be protected everywhere. Many countries support these rights through international agreements.</i>
Arguments AGAINST the Same Laws	1–1.5 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different cultures • Religious values • Political & economic differences 	<i>Opponents believe that the same laws cannot work everywhere. Countries have different cultures, religions, and political or economic systems, which strongly influence their laws.</i>
Cultural Differences	50–60 sec	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National identity • One size doesn't fit all • Respecting traditions 	<i>Laws are closely connected to national identity. One legal system does not fit all countries, so traditions and cultural values must be respected.</i>
Compromise	40–50 sec	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universal core laws • Flexible national laws • Global & local balance 	<i>A possible compromise is to have universal core laws, especially for human rights, while allowing countries to adapt their national laws to local conditions.</i>
Conclusion	30–40 sec	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not all laws should be the same • Universal principles • Diversity is effective 	<i>In conclusion, not all laws should be the same. Universal principles are important, but legal diversity can be more effective. A balance between global values and national traditions is the best solution.</i>

Figure 2. Slide of an oral presentation plan at the formative level of the study

At *the summative stage*, students presented a final poster presentation lasting 5-7 minutes with oral support and answers to questions from the audience. The final presentation was a full-fledged extended presentation using a poster or slides and demonstrating all

components of interactive interaction. Assessment was carried out according to the same criteria, which ensured data compatibility at all stages of the study. An example of a final presentation poster is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Final poster presentation at the summative stage of the study

Quantitative analysis included calculation of mean values (M) for each criterion and comparative analysis of results at three stages of preparation and evaluation.

Student participation in the study was voluntary. All materials were used exclusively for research purposes in compliance with the principles of confidentiality and academic integrity. Students were informed about the objectives of the study, evaluation criteria and permissible forms of use of artificial intelligence tools.

Research Results

Quantitative analysis of the research results was aimed at identifying the dynamics of the development of students' oral communicative competence in the process of project-based learning using poster presentation. The assessment was carried out at the diagnostic, formative, and summative stages using six criteria of the analytical multilevel scale. For each criterion, the average values (M) were calculated.

As presented in *Table 1*, at the diagnostic stage, the average indicators for all criteria ranged from 2.0 to

2.6 points. The lowest values were recorded for the criteria of interactivity and use of communicative strategies, which indicate the limited experience of students in managing oral interaction and performing various communicative roles in an academic context.

At the formative stage, a steady increase in indicators was observed for all criteria. The most positive dynamics was recorded for the criteria of interactivity and the use of communicative strategies, which indicates the high effectiveness of process-oriented forms of learning (group discussions, rehearsals, role-playing) in the development of these components of communicative competence.

At the summative stage, the average indicators for most criteria remained in the range of 2.9–3.3 points. At the same time, a slight decrease was recorded for the criteria of interactivity and the use of communicative strategies compared to the formative stage, which may be due to the increased cognitive load of the final speech and focusing of students on the content and structuring of the presentation.

Table 1

Average values (M) according to the criteria of oral communicative competence at different stages of assessment (n = 48)

Criteria	Diagnostic stage (M)	Formative stage (M)	Summative stage (M)	Growth (%)
Communicative clarity	2,8	3,4	3,9	+39%
Speech organization	2,6	3,3	3,8	+46%
Lexical and grammatical correctness	3,0	3,5	3,9	+30%
Interactivity	2,4	3,2	3,7	+54%
Communicative strategies	2,5	3,3	3,8	+52%
Academic and ethical correctness (including AI)	2,9	3,6	4,1	+41%

As shown in *Table 1*, for all criteria, there is an increase in average scores from the diagnostic to the summative stage, which indicates a positive impact of process-oriented assessment on the development of students' oral communication.

The most pronounced dynamics is recorded for the interactivity criterion (increase +54%). At the diagnostic stage, this indicator had the lowest average value (M = 2.4), which reflected the limited ability of students to interact with the audience, ask clarifying questions and respond to communicative requests. By the summative stage, the average score increased to M = 3.7, which indicates the development of interactive skills in the process of group work, rehearsals and feedback.

A comparable positive dynamics is observed for the criterion of using communicative strategies (increase +52%). The increase in indicators according to this criterion reflects the formation of students' ability to consciously perform various communicative roles in project activities (speaker, moderator, discussion participant). This confirms the importance of procedural stages of project preparation, which are rarely taken into account in traditional assessment.

The indicators of oral expression organization also show significant growth (+46%). If at the diagnostic stage students often presented information fragmentarily and without a clear structure (M = 2.6), then by the final presentation most participants were able to logically build a speech with a clear introduction, main part and conclusion (M = 3.8). This indicates the development of speech planning and structuring skills during phased project work.

According to the criterion of communicative clarity, an increase of 39% was recorded, which indicates the coherence of statements and the ability to adapt speech to the audience. It should be noted that the improvement of this indicator occurred gradually and was

due, in our opinion, to formative feedback in the form of rehearsals and discussions with the teacher at the stage of project preparation.

Relatively less pronounced growth is observed according to the criterion of lexical and grammatical adequacy (+30%). However, the increase in the average score from M = 3.0 to M = 3.9 indicates a more appropriate and conscious use of language tools in oral academic communication.

Special attention is paid to the criterion of academic and ethical correctness (taking into account the use of AI), for which an increase of +41% was recorded. The results show that the inclusion of this criterion in the analytical rubric contributed to the formation of a more responsible attitude among students towards the use of artificial intelligence tools. At the summative stage, students more often demonstrated the conscious use of AI as an auxiliary tool, rather than a source of ready-made oral formulations.

Additional analysis of individual trajectories of students was aimed at identifying temporal differences in the manifestation of interactive and strategic components of oral communication, which is demonstrated in *Table 2*. Comparison of the results of the formative and summative stages showed that all participants in the study (n = 48) demonstrated a high level of final oral performance. At the same time, 13 students (27%) had high indicators according to the criteria of interactivity and use of communicative strategies (M ≥ 3.5) already at the formative stage, while the remaining students had a similar level of these components mainly at the summative stage. This indicates differences in the time of formation and demonstration of communicative skills and confirms the importance of procedural assessment for identifying individual dynamics of oral communication development.

Table 2

Time distribution of achieving a high level of interactive and strategic skills

Student group	Number of students	Percentage (%)
High level at the formative stage (M ≥ 3.5)	13	27
High level achieved primarily at the summative stage	35	73
Total	48	100

The obtained data demonstrate that the use of an analytical rubric and the inclusion of a formative assessment stage allow us to record the development of interactive and strategic components of oral communication, which are not always fully reflected in the results of the final presentation. This confirms the limitations of an assessment based solely on summative indicators and emphasizes the validity of a procedurally oriented approach to assessing oral communication in project-based learning.

Discussion of the results

Analysis of data obtained at the diagnostic, formative and summative stages indicates a positive dynamics of the development of oral communicative competence of first-year students. The most noticeable changes were observed in the increase in clarity and coherence of oral statements, increased confidence in oral explanation of the content of the poster, as well as more active participation of students in group discussions.

Students who demonstrated fragmentary oral speech at the diagnostic stage were mostly able to logically present the main ideas of the project by the time of final presentation, relying on visual material and their own oral comments, rather than on the memorized text.

The results of observations and analysis of reflective materials show that formative assessment has become a significant factor in the development of oral communication. Regular feedback contributed to more successful speech, the correction of mistakes in the process of preparation and the reduction of anxiety before public speaking. The practice of self-assessment and mutual assessment allowed students to critically reflect on their own role in the project and the level of their oral communicative activity. Formative assessment can be considered important for the development of interactive and strategic aspects of speech. The preparation process increases the objectivity and validity of the final assessment, especially in conditions of active use of artificial intelligence tools.

Comparison of formative assessment data with the results of the final poster presentation confirms the reasonableness of shifting the emphasis from the product to the process of preparation, especially in conditions of active use of AI. Oral presentation and discussion allowed to reveal the real level of understanding of the content of the project, which increased the validity and correctness of the assessment and reduced the risk of formal performance of the task.

Limitations

This study has a number of limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results.

First, the study was conducted within a single educational module and included a limited number of first-year students studying a foreign language at level B2. This limits the possibility of generalizing the findings to other levels of language training, educational contexts and disciplines.

Second, the assessment of oral communication relied mostly on the expert opinion of the teacher, which has the risk of being subjective, despite the use of analytical criteria and descriptors.

These limitations identify areas for further research, including expanding the sample, involving control groups and developing mechanisms to increase the reliability and objectivity of oral assessment.

Conclusion

The results of the study confirm that the process-oriented assessment model contributes to increasing the objectivity and transparency of the assessment of oral communication of first-year students, the development of their educational autonomy and a more complete accounting of real communicative activity in the conditions of project-based learning.

The proposed model allows you to shift the emphasis from formal control of the final product to the assessment of the process of forming oral communicative competence, which is especially important in the conditions of the widespread use of artificial intelligence tools. Multi-stage assessment, which includes diagnostic, formative, and summative stages, provides a more valid idea of the development of oral speech and meets modern methodological and ethical requirements of higher education.

References

1. Ajjawi, R., & Boud, D. (2017). Researching feedback dialogue: An interactional analysis approach. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 42(2), 252–265. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2015.1102863>
2. Bearman, M., Dawson, P., Ajjawi, R., Tai, J., & Boud, D. (Eds.). (2020). *Re-imagining university assessment in a digital world*. Springer International Publishing.
3. Beckett, G.H., & Miller, P.C. (2008). Project-based second and foreign language education : past, present, and future. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 30, 412–413. DOI: 10.1017/S0272263108080674
4. British Council. (2025). *Speaking assessment constructs: evolution or revolution in the AI era?* British Council. Retrieved from <https://www.britishcouncil.org/research-insight/speaking-assessment-constructs-evolution-or-revolution-ai-era>
5. Brooks, L. (2009). Interacting in pairs in a test of oral proficiency: Co-constructing a better performance. *Language Testing*, 26(3), 341–366. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265532209104666>
6. Council of Europe (2020). *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment—Companion Volume*. Council of Europe Publishing. <https://www.coe.int/lang-cefr>
7. Fulcher, G. (2015). *Re-examining Language Testing: A Philosophical and Social Inquiry* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315695518>
8. Galaczi, E. D., French, A., Hubbard, C., & Green, A. (2011). *Developing assessment scales for large-scale speaking tests: A multiple-method approach*. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 18(3), 217–237. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2011.574605>
9. Galaczi, E. D., & Taylor, L. (2018). Interactional competence: Conceptualisations, operationalisations, and outstanding questions. *Language Assessment*

- Quarterly*, 15(3), 219–235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2018.1453816>
10. Harding, L. & Kremmel, B. (2016). 25. Teacher assessment literacy and professional development. In D. Tsagari & J. Banerjee (Ed.), *Handbook of Second Language Assessment* (pp. 413–428). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781614513827-027>
11. Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning*. Center for Curriculum Redesign. <https://www.consortios-them.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/sthem-ia-07-holmes-fadel-bialik-artificial-intelligence-in-education-promise-and-implications-for-teaching-and-learning-2019.pdf>
12. Nejad, A. M., & Mahfoodh, O. H. A. (2019). *Assessment of oral presentations: Effectiveness of self-, peer-, and teacher assessments*. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(3), 615–632. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2019.12337a>
13. O'Dowd, R., & O'Rourke, B. (2019). New developments in virtual exchange in foreign language education. *Language Learning & Technology*, 23(3), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.64152/10125/44690>
14. Parmigiani, D., Nicchia, E., Murgia, E., & Ingersoll, M. (2024). *Formative assessment in higher education: An exploratory study within programs for professionals in education*. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/education/articles/10.3389/feduc.2024.1366215>
15. Panadero, E., Andrade, H.L., & Brookhart, S.M. (2018). Fusing self-regulated learning and formative assessment: a roadmap of where we are, how we got here, and where we are going. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 45, 13–31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-018-0258-y>
16. Pinto-Llorente, A. M., & Izquierdo-Álvarez, V. (2024). Digital Learning Ecosystem to Enhance Formative Assessment in Second Language Acquisition in Higher Education. *Sustainability*, 16(11), 4687. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16114687>
17. Poole, D. L., & Mackworth, A. K. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence: Foundations of Computational Agents* (3rd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
18. Selwyn, N. (2023). *Artificial intelligence and education: Critical perspectives on new technologies*. Polity Press.
19. Stephenson, Z., Johnson-Glauch, N., & Cruchley, S. (2025). *Interventions and facilitators of oral assessment performance in higher education: A systematic review*. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2025.2504621>
20. Stoller, F. L. (2006). *Establishing a theoretical foundation for project-based learning in second and foreign language contexts*. In G. H. Beckett & P. C. Miller (Eds.), *Project-based second and foreign language education* (pp. 19–40). Lawrence Erlbaum.
21. Stoyanoff, S., & Chapelle, C. A. (Eds.). (2021). *The Routledge handbook of language assessment*. Routledge. <https://www.routledge.com/The-Routledge-Handbook-of-Language-Assessment/Stoyanoff-Chapelle/p/book/9780367204918>
22. Wiliam, D. (2011). What is assessment for learning? *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 37(1), 3–14 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.STUEDUC.2011.03.001>
23. Winstone, N., & Carless, D. (2019). *Designing Effective Feedback Processes in Higher Education: A Learning-Focused Approach* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351115940>
24. Fan, J., & Yan, X. (2020). Assessing Speaking Proficiency: A Narrative Review of Speaking Assessment Research Within the Argument-Based Validation Framework. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 330. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00330>